

Fig. 4

Figure 4. HI 21cm emission spectrum toward IRAS 19448–0234 extracted from the HI4PI all-sky survey (HI4PI Collaboration 2016) using the EBHIS data (Effelsberg 100m telescope, angular resolution 16.2', extraction beam 0.5°). Left panel: full velocity profile from –100 to +100 km/s LSR; the spectrum is consistent with zero emission outside this range. Right panel: zoom on the main emission component, with the FWHM indicated. A prominent narrow component is detected at $V_{\text{LSR}} = +2.7$ km/s with peak brightness temperature $T_{\text{B}} = 42.8$ K and $\text{FWHM} \approx 4.4$ km/s, characteristic of cold neutral hydrogen. A secondary broader component is visible at $V_{\text{LSR}} \approx +20$ km/s. The total HI column density along this sightline is $N(\text{HI}) = 7.5 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (EBHIS). The low LSR velocity of the main component is consistent with the Bayestar photometric distance of ~ 200 pc.